

Supplementary Table S1. Statistical table of sequencing quantity per sample.

Sample-ID	Input	Filtered	Denoised	Merged	Non-chimeric
D01	87887	79923	78105	74835	66292
D02	67853	59163	53497	47710	43425
D03	53391	47318	42356	35708	31535
D04	81679	73634	72027	66403	55656
D05	71953	60889	57148	54002	50001
D06	93781	84063	82301	74942	62108
D07	54031	47631	45158	42185	33250
D08	54027	40338	35476	32608	30749
D09	86419	77514	76062	70125	59180
D10	87249	76720	75554	72211	56667
D11	76525	68925	67519	65558	62543
D12	89290	81125	80013	76438	66559
W1	57539	52486	49489	45014	35271
W2	88979	82931	80638	76255	69991
W3	52969	46156	41224	37147	31726
W4	81127	68184	65890	60198	54355
W5	86991	79406	76097	66369	57919
W6	87705	79062	76332	67309	56036
W7	75814	70660	67621	61411	46303
W8	78092	72695	70301	62208	55225

D01-D12 represent the samples collected in domestic mallards, and W1-W8 represent the samples collected in wild mallards.

Supplementary Table S2. ASV classification table for two groups of mallards.

Sample	Kingdom	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species	ASV abundance
DM01	1	18	49	64	85	66	18	363
DM02	1	19	55	84	119	117	41	862
DM03	1	22	54	76	120	143	57	898
DM04	1	14	26	39	70	99	52	490
DM05	1	13	31	44	74	89	40	485
DM06	1	9	22	42	68	97	59	552
DM07	1	17	42	49	66	70	38	356
DM08	1	14	38	49	67	68	29	413
DM09	1	9	20	32	60	74	45	460
DM10	1	8	21	32	54	59	28	274
DM11	1	15	41	57	82	72	30	281
DM12	1	8	19	33	59	67	31	277
WM1	1	15	37	55	81	95	41	463
WM2	2	20	47	73	111	133	55	546
WM3	2	20	50	64	95	97	42	610
WM4	1	11	26	41	73	86	42	469
WM5	2	26	47	81	114	132	65	956
WM6	2	16	32	57	97	135	73	736
WM7	1	20	58	83	126	125	51	687
WM8	1	14	31	49	83	126	72	765
SUM	2	38	101	168	236	409	245	7555

DM01-DM12 represent the samples collected in domestic mallards, and WM1-WM8 represent the samples collected in wild mallards.